

ANEURYSM DISEASE, ITS CAUSES AND TREATMENT METHODS.

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Аннотация: Аневризма представляет собой локальное расширение сосуда с постепенным истончением его стенки. Процесс является необратимым, со временем под воздействием давления кровотока выпячивание только увеличивается и, однажды, может разорваться. Это приводит к внутреннему артериальному кровотечению.

Ключевые слова: Заболеваниие, артерии вены, генетических синдромов, стенки сердца, атеросклероз.

Abstract: An aneurysm is a local expansion of a vessel with gradual thinning of its wall. The process is irreversible, over time, under the influence of blood flow pressure, the protrusion only increases and, one day, can rupture. This leads to internal arterial bleeding.

Keywords: Disease, arteries, veins, genetic syndromes, heart walls, atherosclerosis.

Introduction: An aneurysm is an abnormal bulge in the wall of a blood vessel or This bulge occurs due to a weakness in the wall of the vessel or heart, which can be caused by a variety of factors, including birth defects, atherosclerosis, injury, infection, and inflammation.

The wall of the vessel or heart becomes thinner and less elastic in a certain area. Under the pressure of the blood, this weak spot begins to bulge, forming a sac-like or spindle-shaped dilation. Over time, an aneurysm can increase in size. An aneurysm can occur in any blood vessel in the body, but is most Aorta: The largest blood vessel that leaves the heart. An aortic aneurysm can be abdominal (in the abdomen) or thoracic (in the chest).

Cerebral arteries: An aneurysm in the brain can cause a stroke if it ruptures. Peripheral arteries: In the legs, groin, or neck. Heart: A cardiac aneurysm is usually.

Main part: Atherosclerosis: This is the most common cause of aneurysms, especially aortic and peripheral artery aneurysms. The deposition of cholesterol, fats, and other substances on the walls of arteries leads to the formation of atherosclerotic plaques. These plaques make the vessel walls stiff, less elastic, and more vulnerable to damage and bulging under the pressure of blood.

Age-related changes: As we age, the walls of our blood vessels naturally lose their elasticity and strength, which can contribute to the development of aneurysms. Degeneration of elastic fibers and collagen in the vessel wall occurs.

Genetic and congenital factors, Hereditary connective tissue disorders: Some genetic disorders, such as Marfan syndrome, Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, and neurofibromatosis type 1, are characterized by defects in the structure of collagen and elastin, the main components of the connective tissue that make up the walls of blood vessels. This makes them weaker and more susceptible to aneurysms.

Congenital defects of the vessel wall: In rare cases, people can be born with areas of weakened vessel walls, predisposing them to the development of aneurysms.

Family history: Having close relatives with aneurysms can increase the risk of developing the condition, even in the absence of known genetic syndromes. External influences and acquired conditions.

Hypertension (high blood pressure): Constantly increased pressure on the vessel walls can weaken them over time and contribute to the formation of aneurysms.

Blunt or penetrating trauma to blood vessels can damage the vessel wall and lead to the development of traumatic aneurysms, sometimes long after the injury.

Rare bacterial or fungal infections can affect the walls of arteries (mitotic aneurysms), causing them to weaken and bulge.

Inflammatory vascular diseases (vasculitides): Some autoimmune or inflammatory diseases, such as polyarthritis nodosa or polyarthritis nodosa, can cause inflammation of the vessel walls, causing damage and aneurysms.

Smoking damages the vessel walls, contributing to the development of atherosclerosis and increasing the risk of aneurysms. **Specific causes of cardiac aneurysms. Coronary artery disease (CAD) and myocardial infarction:** A left ventricular aneurysm is often a complication of a large myocardial infarction. The damaged heart muscle becomes thinner and bulges under the pressure of blood.

Chronic heart failure: Long-term stress on the heart can lead to structural changes, including the formation of aneurysms.

Infective endocarditis: An infection of the inner lining of the heart can damage and weaken the wall of the ventricle, causing an aneurysm.

Analysis and results: Angiography (arteriography): This is an invasive procedure in which a catheter is inserted into a blood vessel and a contrast agent is injected through it. The X-ray images produced during this procedure clearly show the vessels and identify aneurysms. Although it is the "gold standard" for diagnosing vascular disease, it is used less frequently due to its invasiveness and risk of complications, usually when planning treatment.

Clinical examination and history. A physician may suspect an aneurysm based on the patient's symptoms (e.g., abdominal or back pain with an abdominal aortic aneurysm, headache with a cerebral aneurysm) and the physical examination. Family history is also important, as some aneurysms may be linked to a genetic predisposition. Transesophageal echocardiography (TEE): A specialized ultrasound that inserts a transducer into the esophagus, allowing for a clearer picture of the aorta, especially the thoracic region.

Lumbar puncture: May be performed if a subarachnoid hemorrhage (ruptured brain aneurysm) is suspected, to look for blood in the cerebrospinal fluid.

Treatment: Complete treatment of a cerebral aneurysm is a complex and multifaceted process that depends on many factors, including: 1. The size, shape, and location of the aneurysm. 2. The presence or absence of symptoms. 3. The patient's health status. 4. The risk of aneurysm rupture. 5. The patient's age. There is no one-size-fits-all approach to treatment, and the decision is made individually by a neurosurgeon or team of specialists after careful evaluation of all factors. The main goals of treatment are to prevent aneurysm rupture and subsequent bleeding into the brain (subarachnoid hemorrhage), which can lead to severe neurological consequences and even death.

In some cases, especially for small, asymptomatic aneurysms with a low risk of rupture, observation may be the preferred approach. This includes:

Regular screening: Periodic neuroimaging studies (MRI or CT angiography) to monitor the size and condition of the aneurysm. The frequency of screening is determined by the physician.

Risk factor management: Managing factors that may increase the risk of rupture, such as high blood pressure, smoking, and alcohol abuse.

Medication: Prescribing medications to control blood pressure, cholesterol, and other underlying medical conditions.

Lifestyle modification: Encouraging healthy eating, regular physical activity, and avoiding stress.

Watching may be the preferred option for older patients with multiple underlying medical conditions or for very small aneurysms where the risk of intervention may outweigh the risk of rupture.

Surgical treatment (open surgery - clipping) Clipping an aneurysm is a traditional surgical procedure that involves the following: Access to the aneurysm: The neurosurgeon performs a craniotomy (opening the skull bone) to gain access to the brain vessels and the aneurysm.

Isolation of the aneurysm: Under a microscope, the surgeon carefully isolates the neck of the aneurysm (the place where the bulge connects to the main artery).

Clipping: A special titanium clip (clamp) is placed on the neck of the aneurysm, which blocks the blood flow to the aneurysm, isolating it from the rest of the vascular bed. This prevents it from rupturing.

Closing the wound: After checking the reliability of the clipping and the absence of bleeding, the skull bone is returned to its place and the wound is sutured.

Postoperative period and rehabilitation. After any type of aneurysm treatment, the patient requires observation and rehabilitation. This may include:

Stay in the intensive care unit: In the first days after surgery for careful monitoring of the patient's condition. **Pain relief:** To relieve postoperative pain. **Prevention of complications:** Measures to prevent infections, thrombosis and other complications.

Neurological monitoring: Regular assessment of neurological status. **Rehabilitation:** Depending on the presence of neurological deficit, physical therapy, occupational therapy, speech therapy and neuropsychological rehabilitation may be required.

Follow-up examinations: Regular MRI or CT angiography to assess the effectiveness of treatment and identify possible relapses.

In case of aneurysm rupture. Treatment of a ruptured aneurysm is urgent and aimed at stabilizing the patient's condition: Maintaining vital functions.

Prevention of rebleeding. Using surgical clipping or endovascular embolization. **Elimination of the consequences of hemorrhage:** Treatment of vasospasm (narrowing of blood vessels), hydrocephalus and other complications. **Intensive rehabilitation:** To restore lost functions. The prognosis after an aneurysm rupture is serious, and the outcome largely depends on the severity of the hemorrhage, the patient's age, and the presence of concomitant diseases.

Conclusion

An aneurysm is a potentially life-threatening condition that can accompany a person for many years. Therefore, understanding and avoiding risk factors is an important task for maintaining health.

Except for emergency cases, in which open surgery is performed, treatment of aneurysms depends on their size, location, and the risk factors to which the patient is exposed. Small aneurysms that do not cause symptoms and are unlikely to rupture require only periodic monitoring and blood pressure control.

Eat a healthy diet. Avoid high-calorie fatty and salty foods, try to eat more fruits and vegetables, poultry, fish, and nuts.

Monitor blood pressure and engage in regular moderate physical activity.

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